

EFFECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON DIETARY PATTERN OF URBAN POPULATION

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ABSTRACT

The study explores the effects of social media on the dietary habits of individuals in Nagpur city. By examining commonly used social media platforms for nutrition, its awareness, acceptance and application of nutrition-based messages, this research provides insight into how digital engagement influences dietary behaviors. A descriptive research design was utilized with a sample of 144 participants, divided equally between males and females, selected through simple random sampling. Data was collected via a structured questionnaire, and anthropometric data was analyzed using BMI comparisons with WHO standards. A t-test was applied to test for significant differences in the BMI of males and females, revealing no significant difference. The average BMI of males was 22.81 kg/m² (SD = 4.8) and for females, it was 21.78 kg/m² (SD = 4.9). Findings indicate that WhatsApp (97%) and YouTube (79%) are the most frequently used social media platforms among respondents. Majority respondents (85.4%) are aware of general nutrition and health concepts, and many (95.3%) read nutrition-related messages for knowledge and health improvement. However, a notable portion (50.0%) lacks verification of information before sharing. The study reveals that social media influences dietary habits, with many users trying diet plans or recipes and feeling pressured to conform to certain dietary trends and body images promoted online. Despite these influences, there is no significant difference in health status or BMI between males and females. 50 % participants tried diet plans and purchased food and beverages shown on social media, thus following information these platforms. A chi-square test was performed on responses from males and females. The chi-square test results indicated that there is no significant association between male and female responses, as the p-value was greater than 0.05. This suggests that social media influences on dietary habits are similar across genders, supporting the null hypothesis. The research highlights the importance of understanding social media's role in shaping dietary habits, suggesting that public health strategies and social media campaigns should consider these findings to promote healthier eating behaviors. However, limitations such as reliance on self-reported data and the rapidly changing nature of social media trends must be acknowledged.

KEYWORD: Social media, Dietary habits, Nutrition awareness, Descriptive research design, T- test, Healthier eating habits, Gender responses.

INTRODUCTION

Food consumption is one of the most vital daily practices that effect the performance of entire human body throughout the day. Various external factors influence this practice, and social media is one of most significantly affecting it. Social media refers to interactive technologies that facilitate the creation, sharing and aggregation of content, ideas, interests, and other forms of expression through virtual communities and networks. It has become integral parts of many people's lives, providing a means to connect with friends, family, and colleagues as well as share thoughts, ideas, and media. (Dollarhide M, 2024).

The use of social media is increasing in developing

countries. According to latest survey available in India, there are about 462.0 million active social media users which are 33.4% of the demographics (Kemp S, 2024). 95% of the young generation today have social media profile making them biggest user demographic in world. Young generation engages with social media numerous times a day.

1.1 BACKGROUND

Over the past decade, social media has allowed internet users to interact on unlimited topics including health and weight management however, with continued growth of social media, its impact is expanding. Social media is changing the food habits of people through advertisement, news post on different platforms and

through social media influencer.

They enjoy visual platform such as snapchat, TikTok, Instagram and You Tube. Twitter is one of most widely used social media platform. Over 75% of young generation follow at least one influencer on social media (Sudexo.com. 2023). Social media's influencers can be defined as famous content creators with many followers, promoting products and services to inspire other.

Many celebrities are appearing in advertisements and endorsing food that is high in salt and sugar which is ultra-processed and none of the advertisement declares the amount of sugar or salt in product. Young people often turn to social media to gain meals inspiration and are influenced by food friends they see on various platforms. Young people are more impressionable and more likely to copy the food they see online and what their favourite celebrities are eating. Many researchers have indicated that social media can alter our relationship with food. A study predicts that young people are exposed to food marketing around 30-189 times/ week of social media with increase sugar and fast food being most commonly used. (Brown J. et al, 2021).

Celebrities like Ranbir Kapoor advertising for coco cola, Ranveer Singh for thumps up, Deepika Padukone for GoodDay biscuits, Varun Dhawan for Frooti, Salman Khan for Appy Fizz, and Kapil Sharma show endorses Maggi Noodle, Virat Kohli advertised for Domino's Pizza and Yuvraj sing for Cadburys. These celebrities have millions of followers on Instagram and twitter. According to some study, young generations who were exposed to vloggers promoting sugary and fatty snacks went on to eat 26% of more calories than those who didn't watch or read these. (The Quint, 2019).

Famous food influencers like Sanjeev Kapoor, chef Ranveer Brar, Tarla Dalal, dietician Rujuta Diwakar, Pooja Makhija, Laveen Kaur etc have also many followers, generating well balanced easy to recreate food content and contributing to the growing food community on social media. The content, they produced is typically educational in terms of sharing recipes and cooking techniques, thus increasing focus on health and therefore those who engage with their expert content and culinary advice benefit by endorsing their own knowledge and understanding. Expert culinary influencers who promote and educate food content have level of credibility when promoting healthy eating experiences that encourages good habits and expose young people to a wider range of well-balanced meals equipping them with this knowledge and helps them by giving them knowledge base to browse social media without being influenced by misleading or unhealthy content that they may encounter on various site and help them to be more confident of the decisions they make (Sudexo.com, 2023).

Interestingly, many influencers who promote food content do not have an established food or nutrition

background whilst enthusiastic they may not fully understand the impact of what they are promoting to impressionable minds and repercussions that may have over the long run. Influencer all over the social media, some positive and some negative in the context of repetitive and fast paced content and scrolling, it is difficult to break away from their promotions and endorsement and take an objective view.

The impact of social media on the nutritional status of young generation is multifaceted issue with both positive and negative aspects.

Food education is great way to help to control informed decision to support their own health and wellbeing benefits, minimising confusion and give power to young generation and ensure they are confident in their habits and able to contextualise and ignore negative influence.

It is vital to understand how social media impacts eating disorders for e.g. people can easily be influenced by social media without realizing it, when making food related decisions. Therefore, this study explores the effects of social media on food consumption and change in dietary habits.

1.2 HISTORY OF SOCIAL MEDIA

(Zaidi, G. 2024) Social media has evolved from simple messaging and sharing systems to complex platforms integrating multimedia content, real-time interaction, and sophisticated algorithms. It continues to shape how we communicate, share information, and interact with each other globally.

EARLY BEGININGS: BULLETIN BOARD SYSTEM (BBS) AND USENET (1980s-1990s)

- BBS was launched in 1978 and was hosted on personal computers and allowed users to share messages and files.
- Usenet was created in 1980 and functioned as distributed discussion system where users could post articles in news groups.

EARLY ONLINE SERVICES (1980s-1990s)

- CompuServe which was launched in 1969
- AOL (America online): Started in 1985, offering chat rooms emails and gateway to the internet

RISE OF SOCIAL NETWORKS

- Six Degrees (1997): Often considered the first recognizable social networking site, which allowed users to create profile, list their friend and browse friend's lists.
- Live journal (1999): A blogging platform that incorporated social networking features enabling users to follow and interact with each other.
- Friendster (2002) design to connect real-world friends, it allowed users to create profiles, connect with friend, and share content. It became popular quickly but declined due to technical issues and

competition.

- Myspace (2003): it was most popular networking site which allowed users to customize their profiles extensively and share music and videos.

1.3 THE FACEBOOK ERA AND BEYOND

- Facebook (2004): It is launched by Harvard students; it expanded to other universities and then general public. It introduced the news feed in 2006 and became dominant social networking platform globally.
- Twitter (2006): It is introduced the concept of microblogging, allowing users to post short updates (tweets) and follow others. It became a major platform for real time information and communication.
- LinkedIn (2003): It is focused on professional networking, allowing users to connect with colleagues share resume and job search.

Multimedia sharing and new platforms

- YouTube (2005): Revolutionized video sharing, allowing users to upload, and share and view videos. It becomes a major platform for content creator and influencers.
- Instagram (2010): Focused on photo and later video sharing, it introduced filters and became highly popular, especially among volunteer users. Acquired by Facebook in 2012.
- Snapchat (2011): introduced ephemeral messaging, where photos and messages disappears after being viewed. Known for its innovative features like stories and filters.
- TikTok (2016): Originally launched as Douyin in China and rebranded for international markets, it focuses on short-form video content and has become extremely popular among younger audiences.

1.4 CURRENT TRENDS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

- Clubhouse (2020): An audio-based social network that gained popularity for live voice conversations in rooms, catering to the growing interest in audio content.
- Decentralized and Privacy-Focused Platforms: Emerging platforms like Mastodon and Signal emphasize user privacy and decentralized networks, reflecting growing concerns over data privacy.

1.5 EFFECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON USERS

The impact of social media on users is multifaceted, offering significant benefits in connectivity, information dissemination, and self-expression while also posing challenges related to mental health, privacy, and social behaviour. Awareness and mindful usage can help mitigate the negative effects while maximizing the positive aspects of social media.

POSITIVE BENEFITS OF SOCIAL MEDIA

- **Information and education:** (Chau *et al.*, 2018)
 - Social media platforms are powerful tools for disseminating information about nutrition, healthy eating and dietary guidelines.
 - Users can access a wealth of information on various diets, food choice and nutritional facts helping them make more informed decisions about diets.
- **Community support**
 - Social media provides a platform for individuals with similar dietary goals or restriction to connect and form supportive communities. Supportive online communities can offer encouragement, advice and share personal experiences, fostering a sense of belonging and motivation for individuals pursuing healthier dietary habits.
- **Recipe sharing an inspiration**
 - Social media is treasure trove of recipes and cooking ideas. Platforms like Instagram, Pinterest and YouTube are filled with creative and nutritious recipes that can inspire individuals to try new healthy dishes.
 - The visual nature of these platforms makes it easy for users to find visually appealing and appetizing meals ideas. (Annzra Denita, 21 July 2023)
- **Accountability and tracking**
 - Many individuals are using social media to publicly share their health and fitness journeys including their dietary habits.
 - Posting about one's dietary choices can create a sense of accountability, as friends and followers may offer support and encouragement and this public commitment can motivate individual to stick to their health goals. (Royle-Davies 2024, April 23)
- **Access to experts**
 - Social media allows users to connect with nutritionist, dietitians and fitness experts. Professionals can share evidence-based information, answer question and provide personalized advice, making it easier for individuals to receive expert guidance on their dietary habits (Saboia *et al.*, 2020)
- **Promotion of healthy lifestyles**
 - Influencers and organizations on social media often promote healthy lifestyle, including balance diet and regular exercise.
 - Positive role models and influencers can have significant impact on followers, encouraging them to adopt healthier dietary habits an overall wellness practice.
- **Accessibility of health challenges and trends**
 - Social media can help popularize health challenges such as 30-day clean eating or meatless Monday" encourages users to try new dietary habits and

experiment with healthier food choices.

- **Real time updates and trends**

- Social media platforms provide real time updates on nutritional trends, super foods and health-related news. This information can help individuals stay informed about the latest developments in the field of nutrition and adjust their dietary habits accordingly. (Chan *et al.*, 2020)

- **Meal planning and prep Ideas**

- Social media is a valuable resource for meal planning and preparation ideas. Users can take tips, tricks and time-saving strategies for preparing healthy meals, making it easier for them to maintain a nutritious diet, especially in today's busy lifestyles. (Kim, 2024)

- **Cultural exchange**

- Social media connects people from different cultures allowing for the sharing of diverse dietary habits and traditional recipes. This exposure can encourage individuals to incorporate a variety of nutritious foods into their diets (Wibowo *et al.*, 2023)

NEGATIVE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA

- **Misinformation:** Social media platform can be breeding grounds for misinformation about nutrition, diets and health. Misleading advice or fad diets may spread quickly, leading individuals to make unhealthy dietary choices on inaccurate information. (Law *et al.*, 2023)

- **Unrealistic Body Image Standards:** Social media often portrays unrealistic body images, promoting narrow beauty standards. This can contribute to body dissatisfaction and unhealthy dieting practices as individuals strive to achieve an idealized appearance. (Panet. *al.*, 2022)

- **Promotion of fad diets:** Social media platforms are frequently used to promote fad diets that may lack scientific validity or sustainability. Quick-fix diets can be unhealthy and may lead to nutritional deficiencies or eating disorders. (Law *et al.*, 2023)

- **Comparison culture and peer pressure:** The constant exposure to curated and idealized images of food and bodies on social media can foster a culture of comparison. Individuals may feel pressured to conform to certain eating patterns or body types even if they are not suitable for their individual health needs (Jiotsa *et al.*, 2021)

- **Mindless eating and distraction:** Excessive use of social media, especially during meals, can contribute to mindless eating. Individuals may become distracted by their screen, leading to overeating or unhealthy eating habits. (La Marra *et al.*, 2020)

- **Advertisement for unhealthy foods:** Social media platforms often feature advertisements for processed and unhealthy foods. Exposure to these advertisements can influence individual to make poor dietary choice particularly if they are easily swayed by marketing tactics. (Van Der Bendet *al.*, 2022 & Anderson *et al.*, 2021)

- **Lack of personalization:** Social media trend and influencers may promote one-size-fit-all dietary advice, neglecting the importance of personalized nutrition. Individuals have unique needs, and following generic advice may not be suitable for everyone. (Parashar, 2022)

- **Sedentary lifestyle promotion:** While not directly related to dietary habits, social media can contribute to a sedentary lifestyle, as individuals spend extended period sitting and scrolling through their feed, lack of physical activity can impact overall health and contribute to weight-related issues. (Park *et al.*, 2020)

- **Sleep disruption:** Excessive use of social media, especially before bedtime, can contribute to poor sleep quality. Inadequate sleep is associated with disrupted eating patterns and an increased likelihood of making unhealthy food choices. (Serenko *et al.*, 2021)

- **Cyberbullying and mental health impact:** Negative comments, cyber bullying or body shaming on social media platforms can negative impact mental health. Stress and emotional distress may lead to unhealthy coping mechanisms, including changes in dietary habits. (Bansal *et al.*, 2023)

- **Food porn and overeating:** The prevalence of visually appealing food images on social media, often referred to "food porn" can contribute to overeating. Constant exposure to tempting images may trigger cravings and impulsive eating behaviours. (Vermeir *et al.*, 2020)

- It is vital to understand how social media impacts eating disorders for e.g. people can easily be influenced by social media without realizing it, when making food related decisions. Therefore, this study explores the effects of social media on food consumption and change in dietary habits.

- **EFFECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON STUDENTS**

- The effects of social media on students' health and diet are multifaceted, encompassing both physical and mental health aspects as stated in above paragraphs.

- Social media has both positive and negative impacts on students' health and diet. While it can provide valuable information and social support, it can also promote unhealthy behaviors and mental health challenges. Awareness and mindful use of social

media, along with guidance from educators and parents, can help mitigate the negative effects while enhancing the positive aspects. (Husna *et al.*, 2023)

▪ **EFFECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON PEOPLE WITH SIMILAR INTEREST**

Social media has a profound impact on people with similar interests, offering numerous benefits such as community building, information sharing, and collaborative opportunities. However, it also presents challenges like echo chambers, conflict, privacy concerns, overuse, and the spread of misinformation. Balancing the use of social media while being aware of these potential issues can help individuals maximize the positive effects and mitigate the negative ones. (Lenhart, 2015).

▪ **EFFECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON HUMAN HEALTH**

Social media can have wide-ranging effects on human health, encompassing both positive and negative impacts.

Positive Effects on Health are as follows: (Kanchan, 2023)

- **Mental Health Support:** Community and Support Groups: Social media platforms host various support groups where individuals can share experiences and receive emotional support, helping those dealing with mental health issues like depression, anxiety, and grief.
- **Access to Information:** Users can access a wealth of information about mental health, coping strategies, and wellness tips from professionals and peers.
- **Health Education and Awareness:** Public Health Campaigns: Organizations use social media to spread awareness about diseases, vaccination, healthy living, and preventive measures, reaching a broad audience quickly.
- **Fitness and Nutrition Tips:** There is a plethora of content related to fitness routines, healthy eating, and lifestyle changes that can motivate users to adopt healthier habits.
- **Telehealth and Online Consultations:** Remote Health Services: social media and related platforms facilitate telehealth services, allowing patients to consult healthcare providers remotely, which can be particularly beneficial in underserved areas.
- **Peer Support and Motivation**
 - **Fitness Challenges:** Online fitness challenges and groups can motivate individuals to stay active and pursue their health goals.
 - **Tracking Progress:** Many people share their health journeys on social media, receiving encouragement and accountability from their networks.

Negative Effects on Health are as follows: (Roy and Stegner, 2023)

- **Mental Health Issues**
 - **Anxiety and Depression:** Excessive use of social media can lead to feelings of inadequacy, anxiety, and depression, particularly due to comparisons with others and exposure to cyberbullying.
 - **Addiction:** Social media can be addictive, leading to compulsive use that interferes with daily life, sleep, and personal relationships.
- **Physical Health Problems**
 - **Sedentary Lifestyle:** Spending excessive time on social media can contribute to a sedentary lifestyle, increasing the risk of obesity, cardiovascular diseases, and other health issues.
 - **Sleep Disturbances:** The blue light emitted by screens and the habit of checking social media late at night can disrupt sleep patterns, leading to sleep deprivation and related health problems.
- **Impact on Eating Habits**
 - **Unhealthy Diet Trends:** Social media can promote unhealthy diet trends and unrealistic body standards, leading to poor eating habits and disorders like anorexia, bulimia, and orthorexia.
 - **Influence of Food Marketing:** The promotion of fast food and sugary drinks on social media can influence users, particularly young people, to make unhealthy dietary choices.
- **Privacy and Security Concerns**
 - **Data Privacy:** Sharing personal health information on social media can lead to privacy breaches and misuse of data.
 - **Cyberbullying and Harassment:** Negative interactions on social media, including harassment and cyberbullying, can severely impact mental health.

ROLE OF NUTRITION IN MAINTAINING HEALTH

Nutrition plays a fundamental role in maintaining health by providing the body with the necessary nutrients required for various physiological functions. Good nutrition is a cornerstone of health, supporting bodily functions, enhancing mental well-being, and reducing the risk of chronic diseases. A balanced diet rich in essential nutrients helps maintain overall health, supports growth and development, boosts the immune system, and promotes healthy weight and digestion. By following nutritional guidelines and making mindful food choices, individuals can optimize their health and well-being.

1.7. AIM AND OBJECTIVES, HYPOTHESIS FORMULATIONS, SCOPE, AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1.7.1 AIM: To study the effects of social media on Dietary habits of urban population in Nagpur city.

1.7.2 OBJECTIVES

- To study demographic status of respondents.

- To identify commonly used social medias.
- To assess health status of individuals by using BMI and compare with standards of WHO (Asians).
- To study awareness on nutrition and reason behind reading nutritional messages in subjects.
- To study acceptance of nutritional based messages on social media and their application in dietary habits.
- To statistically compare the responses of males and females.

1.7.3 HYPOTHESIS FRAMED

- There is no real difference in the health status of individuals when compared to WHO standard
- There is no real significant difference between responses of males and females and if there is, it is just by chance.

1.7.4 SIGNIFICANCE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

Studying the effects of social media on dietary habits of young individual is essential for addressing public health concerns, understanding consumer behaviour, and developing effective intervention to promote healthy eating habits in today's digital age.

LIMITATIONS

- Data gathered for such studies often relies on self-reported information from participants which can be subject to various biases, where participant may respond in ways they believe are socially acceptable rather than truthfully reflecting their behaviours.
- Social media platforms and trends are constantly changing and evolving so it's challenging to keep up with latest developments.
- Longitudinal studies that track individual over extended periods of time are necessary to understand the long-term inputs, but they are often resource-intensive and time-consuming.
- It is difficult to isolate the specific influence of social media on dietary habits as they are influenced by many other factors.

1. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This Literature reviews aims to explore and analyse the impacts of social media on dietary habits of younger generation. Social media has become an integral part of modern society and its influence on various aspects of life, including dietary choices, is undeniable. These reviews examine relevant studies, research articles and publications to gain insight into the relationship between social media and dietary habits among young generation. The findings reveal both positive and negative effects of social media on dietary habits, highlighting the need for further research and interventions to promote healthy eating behaviours in younger generation.

- Nadinizeeni *et al.*, (2024) conducted study which aimed to assess the effects of junk food-related

Instagram content exposure on body image, overall mood and cravings in people. A randomized crossover experimental design was used. After filling out a baseline survey, participants (n = 63, aged 18–24) browsed either a control Instagram account feed or an account rich in junk food images during 15 min. They then filled a short survey evaluating their state BI, mood, and cravings (T1). After a 1-week washout period (T2), participants browsed the other account type followed by the same short survey as in T1. Results showed that exposure to junk food content was associated with increased feelings of hunger, stress, sadness, and exhaustion, in addition to higher salty, savoury, and fatty food cravings. In conclusion, exposure to junk-food related content on social media negatively affects mood and cravings, subsequently influencing food choices. The present findings shed light on the need for interventions aimed at providing cognitive and emotional competencies for enhancing media literacy and promoting mindful social media use.

- Law *et al.*, (2023) conducted study titled 'Exploring the perceived influence of social media use on disordered eating in nutrition and dietetics students. This study aimed to investigate the perceived impact of social media on eating. One to one in-depth semi-structured interview were conducted from university students in UK. Data was thematically analysed to identify key themes. Results suggested that social media may provide students with useful tool for exploration of new recipes thus enabling them to improve their eating behaviours however student also showed high levels of objective aware regarding the problems associated with social media including presence of misinformation body image dissatisfaction social pressures and disordered eating. It was concluded that future research should investigate ways to mitigate the negative impact of social media use.
- Li (2024) did study on paper titled 'the effects of social media on mental health: A study of young Adults in United States. This study examines the effects of social media on health of young adults. The methodology used was the experiment was performed as survey and was conducted to assess the association between the social media use and depression and quantitative method was used. The results corroborated earlier research that suggested that excessive social media use, particularly among individuals may have detrimental effects on mental health.
- Kanchan *et al.*, (2023) conducted research on social media's role and its impact on public health: a narrative review. It aimed to conduct an introductory study of the existing published literature on why to choose and how to use social media to obtain population health information and to gain

knowledge about various health sectors. They search for publications using databases like PubMed, NCBI, and google scholar and combines 2022 social media usage statistics from PWC, Infographics, and Statista online websites. Their findings reflected the benefits and drawbacks of using web platforms and how they impact public health ethically, professionally and socially. They also discovered that social media's impact on public health concerns is both positive and negative, and they attempted to explain how social networks are assisting people in achieving health, which is still a source of much debate.

- Cho *et al.*, (2023) conducted this study titled 'the bright and dark sides of social media use during covid-19 lockdown: Contrasting social media effects through social liability vs social support'. This Study examined the social and psychological impacts of social media usage during the COVID-19 pandemic have provided inconsistent and inconclusive findings. Social media were found to be a source of both social support and anxiety as well as fear. The data for this research was collected through an online survey in May 2020 in the U.S. This study employed measures that have been validated in the existing literature and were reliable (Cronbach's alphas $>.70$, ranging from 0.76 to 0.92). All measures were based on a seven-point Likert scale, except for social media use which was based on a five-point Likert scale. The findings show that social media usage has double-edged effects. When social media usage is associated with increased perceived social support, it has a favourable impact on cognitive appraisals. In contrast, when social media usage results in perceived social liability, it is associated with higher levels of negative emotions through its detrimental effects on cognitive appraisals. The study makes significant theoretical contributions by demonstrating two distinct mechanisms underlying social media effects.
- Van Der Bend *et al.*, (2022) aimed to study adolescent exposure to and evaluation of food promotions on social media -A multi method approach. Australian adolescent ages 13-16 yrs. joined one to one zoomed meeting with researchers on device they normally used on social media. Next, participants answered questions about their awareness and appreciation of SMFPs. Screenshots of SMFPs were de-identified and analysed. The study included 35 adolescents aged 14.4 (± 1.2) years (boys: $n = 18$; girls: $n = 17$). During a total of 1000 min of viewing time, 1801 unbranded ($n = 1221$) and branded ($n = 580$) SMFPs were identified. A majority of SMFPs (62%) were embedded into celebrity influencer or entertaining content (e.g., vlogs, cooking videos, streamed TV content). It was concluded that adolescents' SMFP exposure mostly concerns unhealthy foods, shown in advertisements and other food-related posts, which are integrated into a wide variety of entertainment that is appreciated by adolescents.
- Kucharczak *et al.*, (2022) studied social media's influence on adolescents' food choices; the aim of this systematic review was to investigate the social media's food and beverages advertisement's role in influencing adolescent's food choices by appraising published literature. A PECO questionnaire was developed to guide this review and asked how adolescent who use SM are influenced by food and beverages advertisement found on social media. 234 articles were assessed by title and abstract and against the inclusion criteria, resulting in 197 records being excluded. The findings from this study support and expand upon existing research to help fill a gap in knowledge regarding SM's influence on adolescents' food choices. The two key findings of increased ability to recall unhealthy food, beverages, and brands and celebrity/influencer involvement with food being advertised illustrate the potential impact SM can have when promoting food and beverage products. It was concluded that SM may have some degree of influence on adolescents' food choices. Adolescents had increased ability to recall unhealthy food, beverages, and brands and favoured products that were advertised involving celebrities/influencers.
- Alwafi *et al.*, (2022) conducted a cross-sectional study using an online survey in Saudi Arabia. The topic was the impact of social media influencers on food consumption which was a cross-sectional web-based survey. A convenience sample of eligible participants was used to recruit the study participants. Participants were invited to participate in this study through social media (Facebook, Twitter, Snapchat, and Instagram) to achieve the study's aim, a 32-item questionnaire was distributed. It is comprised of two sections. The first section (14 items) asked the participants about their sociodemographic characteristics. The second section (18 items) explored the impact of social media influencers on food consumption. Data were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software, version 27 (IBM Corp, Armonk, NY, USA). Categorical variables were reported as frequencies and percentages. The result highlighted that social media influences the diet of around one-fifth of the study participants. Using the median score as the cut-off point for being influenced by social media, we (found that males were less likely to be affected by social media than females. The participants' age was negatively associated with their attitudes towards social media and their diet. Bachelor's degree holders were the most affected by social media compared to participants with lower education. Participants with obesity and participants who exercised regularly and had tried a diet to lose

weight were more likely to be affected by social media. Followers of social media influencers were ten times more likely to be affected by social media than others. It was concluded that social media platforms may have a negative impact on food consumption and obesity. Future studies to investigate this association and factors associated with the negative effect of social media on food consumption are warranted.

- Sabbagh *et al.*, (2022) studied for Analysing credibility of UK social media influencer's weight management blogs. It was a pilot study done and this study systematically assessed the credibility of UK social media influencer online weight management information against evidence-based advice, piloting a pre-prepared credibility checklist with aim to offer an initial assessment of patterning of this information online. Blogs and individual post of SMI were coded systemically by single coder against a pre-prepared checklist of credibility indicators. The result suggests that social media influencer weight management blogs are often not credible. The findings suggest that majority of the bloggers failed in fundamental areas. Many of them presented opinion as facts and failed to provide evidence-based references for nutritional claims.
- Mori *et al.*, (2022) aimed to study images of bodies in mass and social media and body dissatisfaction. The role of internalization and self-discrepancy; The study examines the influence on body dissatisfaction of viewed images of bodies transmitted over mass media and social media, as mediated by the internalization of body ideals through media and self-discrepancy (the difference between the perceived actual self and perceived ideal self). In this study, the images of bodies individuals view in their everyday media diet are estimated using a newly developed pictorial scale for women (thinness) and men (muscularity). For participants, the perceived body image is formed through mass media (magazines, TV) and social media (Facebook, YouTube, Instagram and snapchat). The self-discrepancy theory is then used to explain the effect of images of bodies in the media on the internalization of these body ideals and body dissatisfaction. Results show that Facebook and YouTube shape ideals perceived to be prevalent in the media, negatively influencing internalization and self-discrepancy. Self-discrepancy, in turn, increases body dissatisfaction. However, for males, the perceived body ideals in the media did not affect body dissatisfaction, internalization, or self-discrepancy. These results emphasize between female and male concerns regarding body image.
- Jeong *et al.*, (2022) conducted study "How does adolescents' usage of social media affect their dietary satisfaction? It was done to verify meaningful relationships between adolescent usage of social media and their food consumption behaviour. The study used 2 analysis methods t-test and structural equation modelling. The study proposes that food consumption behaviour showed significant differences between users and non-users of social media in adolescent. A study found that adolescents who frequently use social media are more likely to try new foods, avoid potentially harmful foods, and prefer convenience foods such as home meal replacements, eating out, or food delivery. This shift towards convenience foods was linked to lower dietary satisfaction among adolescents. The study suggests the need for government regulations and quality improvements from food companies to address these trends.
- Eser Durmaz *et al.*, (2022) aimed to evaluate the effects of emotional eating and social media on nutritional behaviour and obesity in university students receiving distance education during the pandemic. The data was collected by online questionnaire. Cross sectional study was performed with 1000 undergraduate. A p value less than .05 was considered as statistically significant for statistical tests. It was concluded that that students who receive distance education, social media affects eating behaviour, BMI, and emotional eating and these effects may increase the risk of overweight /obesity.
- Filippone *et al.*, (2022) conducted study titled 'The relationship between social media exposure, food craving, cognitive impulsivity and cognitive restraint'. They analysed the psychological and eating processes through which exposure to social media may lead to the development of food craving and problematic eating behaviours. A total 103 young adult men and women answered questionnaire meaning their impulsivity, eating habits, food craving and time exposure to social media. In result correlational link between time exposure to social media and food cravings scores was found.
- Grover *et al.*, (2022 Science Direct) published article 'The evolution of social media influence'- A literature review and research agenda. This article presents social media influence phenomenon within an individual. It tries to investigate social media influence at individual level with respect to different contexts such as organization, marketplace, and social environment. The method classification scheme for studying social media influence on an individual had been adapted from Cao *et al.* (2015), Zhang and Li (2005); and Zhang *et al.* (2009). The methods had been divided into two components: empirical and non-empirical. Empirical had been further divided into quantitative, qualitative and other. The study on the basis of the finding

concludes social media has a tremendous influence on an individual. Social media enables an individual to connect, share, access and receive information across the borders.

- Vaingankar *et al.*, (2022) conducted study titled 'Social media-driven routes to positive mental health among youth: qualitative enquiry and concept mapping study'. This study explored lives experiences of youth to understand how social media use can contribute to positive mental health among youth. Method use was semi-structured interviews and 11 focus group discussions we conducted with male and female. Conclusion highlighted the integral role of social media in lives of today's youth and indicate that they can offer opportunities for positive influence personal expression and social support, thus contributing to positive mental health among youth.
- Al Ali *et al.*, (2021) conducted study to assess impact of social media on dietary factor and physical activity of Jordanian university students. A cross-sectional correlational design was used and multistage random sampling technique was used to recruit participants in this study. The self-reported questionnaire developed by Hill (Citation2013) was used to collect data from the students. Multiple response analyses were used to describe the frequency of the use of social media for health-related behaviours. The independent samples t-test and Chi-square test were used to assess the relationship between the students' actual physical activity and their perceptions about their health, diet, and physical activity and to compare between students who used social media for health-related messages and those who did not. The level of significance was set at $P < 0.05$. The results of this study indicate that university students in their everyday life widely use social media, and many students rely on these sites as a source of information related to health, diet, and physical activity. It was concluded that student rely on social sites very much and it can be used positively for promoting health practices.
- Aichner *et al.*, (2021) conducted the study titled 'the Twenty-Five years of social media: Review of social media applications and definitions from 1994 to 2019'. In this article the authors present the results from structured review of the literature, identifying and analysing the most quoted and dominant definitions of social media. Method used was to conduct a systematic literature review (SLR). Using a multi-step SLR approach as recommended by Tranfield, structurally examined the literature between 1994 and 2019 to find all relevant SM definitions to identify the major differences and commonalities. After identifying 88 potential papers, all the articles were read to find original

definitions for SM or related terms. The results were in line with previous research about the evolution of SM literature, which concluded that SM definitions changed over time, namely from platforms for socializing in the past to tools for information aggregation.⁴⁵ Similarly, Kapoor *et al.*⁴⁵ found that there was an evolution in SM definitions and a cutin the early 2010. It showed that there is no single or commonly accepted definition, but that several definitions have been co-existing and found broad acceptance in literature. Overall, this research helped in comparing findings from SM literature more easily and avoid misinterpretations of past and future research.

- Smit *et al.*, (2019) conducted study named "The impact of social media influencers on children's dietary behaviour'. They examined the impact of vlogs on children's unhealthy dietary behaviours. They analyse the longitudinal relations between children's frequency of watching vlogs and their consumption of unhealthy beverages and snacks. Structural path modelling analyses of 3 waves of data with 1-year intervals showed that children's self-reported frequency of watching vlogs influence consumption of unhealthy beverages 2 yrs. later.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

INTRODUCTION

Research methodology is a critical aspect of conducting effective and credible research. It provides a systematic framework for investigating problems, generating knowledge, and advancing scientific understanding. By carefully selecting and applying appropriate research methods, researchers can ensure their findings are valid, reliable, and applicable to real-world situations. Understanding and adhering to sound research methodologies is essential for producing high-quality, impactful research. It truly encompasses the concepts such as paradigm, theoretical model and phases and qualitative and quantitative techniques. The present study was carried out to assess the effects of social media on dietary habits of young generation.

METODOLOGY

The methodology of this study includes the following topics

1. Study area
2. Research design and study subjects
3. Size of sample and sampling procedures
4. Duration of study
5. Data collection methods
6. Statistical analysis

3.1 Study Area and target population: The study was conducted in Nagpur city of Maharashtra between the age group of 15-45 years using the Questionnaire technique.

3.2 Research Design: This study made use of

descriptive research, which helps in describing the characteristics of a situation, problem or phenomenon. An observational study was undertaken.

3.3 Sampling Procedure, Sampling Type and Size of Sample

- **Sampling Procedure:** The selection of a sample is a fundamental aspect of research design that significantly impacts the validity and reliability of the study's findings.
- **Sampling Type:** Purposive random and non-probability sampling method was applied
- **Size of sample:** Out of 200 responses, 72 males and 72 females were selected randomly so total 144 numbers of subjects were selected for the study.

3.4 Duration of Study: The present study was undertaken for months from January -April 2024

3.5 Compilation of data and tool used: The method used in the present study to collect data was from structured questionnaire. Based on objectives and

hypothesis framed, each subject had to answer all the questions framed in the questionnaire. The questionnaire had 25 question which were divided into 3 parts such as Demographic Data questions, Health assessment questions and Research-based questions. They are as follows

- A. **Demographic Data:** Three questions were included in this section.
 - Age
 - Gender
 - Qualification
- B. **Health assessment by BMI:** 3 questions were included in this section
 - I- ANTHROPOMETRIC DATA
 - Height in Metre
 - Weight in Kg
 - II- History of any chronic illness
- C. **Research-Based: Questions were included in this section**

3.6 Questionnaire

Table 3.1: Classification of questions according to their objectives.

Objectives	Total questions	Remarks
To find demographic status of respondents.	3	Age, gender and qualifications of respondents
To list the most commonly used social media	2	Subject could choose more than one options
To assess health status of individuals	3	Anthropometric measurement and history of any chronic illness
To study the awareness about nutrition and health among the subjects reason behind reading nutritional post on SM	5	Direct question on nutrition Question on subject's attitude towards nutrition-based messages on social media
To study the acceptance of nutrition-based message on socialmedia and its application in dietary habits	12	(6) Question on acceptance (6) Question on application

Questionnaire is attached in Appendix A

3.7 Statistical Analysis: To find results; responses were analysed with objective using statistical charts to reach the conclusion

- (I) To find a significant difference between the BMI of males and females, a parametric test, the t-test, is applied

Hypothesis framed as:

Null hypothesis: $H_0 =$ There is no significant difference in Male and Female BMI.

T-test is a type of inferential statistic used to determine if there is a significant difference between the means of two groups, which may be related in certain features. A t-test is used as a hypothesis testing tool, which allows testing of an assumption applicable to a population. T-Test Assumption are.

1. The first assumption made regarding t-test concerns the scale of measurement. The assumption for the t-test is that the scale of measurement applied to the data collected follows a continuous or ordinal scale.
2. The second assumption made is that of a simple random, that the data is collected from the representative, randomly selected portion of the total population.

3. The third assumption is the data, when plotted result in a normal distribution, bell shaped distribution curve. In present study parametric test used for checking the significance was t-test two tail with unequal variance due to following factors

- A) Number of questions for responses < 30
- B) Two tail, as we assume significant difference in responses
- C) Variance of population is unknown

- (II) The chi-square test of independence is a statistical method used for non-parametric data and determines if there is a significant association between the observed frequencies of categorical variables in different groups.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For present study, Total 144 responses were taken from questionnaire given to subjects in Nagpur city. These responses were taken for finding results.

4.1. Demographic Data: It contains 3 questions which includes: Age, Gender and Occupation.

4.1.1. Age: Different people from age group between 15 to 45 was taken.

4.1 Distribution of subjects based on age group.

Age	No of persons	Percentage
15-25	82	56.94%
26-35	29	20.13%
36-45	33	22.93%

The age distribution among the participants is varied, encompassing individuals from 15 to 45 years. The largest segment, accounting for 56.94%, comprises 82 individuals aged between 15 to 25 years. The next

significant age group was 26 to 35 years, representing 20.13% of the subjects with 29 individuals. The final age group, 36 to 45 years, which includes 33 participants, making up 22.93% of the subject.

4.1.2. Gender: In present study 72 male and 72 females were selected.

Fig: 1 Percentage distribution according to gender. The above Graph shows 72 male and 72 females in study.

4.1.3. Educational Qualification

Table 4.2 Distribution of subjects based on education.

Education	No of persons	Percentage
10 th Standard	44	30.50%
12 th Standard	24	16.6%
Graduates	44	30.56%
Post Graduated	32	22.22%

The educational background of the participants revealed a diverse range of qualifications. A majority portion of the participants, 44 individuals (30.56%), were graduates. Postgraduates constitute 22.22% of the subject, with 32 individuals holding advanced degrees. Interestingly, 44 participants (30.50%) were still in the

10th class, indicating a younger demographic still engaged in their secondary education. Additionally, 24 individuals (16.6%) were in the 12th class, representing those nearing the completion of their secondary education.

4.1.4. History of any chronic illness

Fig 2: Percentage distribution of chronic diseases in whole population.

21.53% of population had history of chronic disease (like hyperacidity, hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, hypertension, joints pain, allergies, migraine and any

other), while 78.47 percentage of population had no history of chronic diseases.

Fig 3: Percentage distribution according to gender.

The above graph of study showed 42.36% of males had chronic diseases, and 36.11 % of females had history of chronic diseases listed. In females, 25 subjects had history of chronic disease while in male, 16 subjects had history of chronic disease. 103 (78.47%) people don't have any history of chronic illness. The data highlighted prevalence of chronic disease was slightly higher in females than in males.

of subjects to get the BMI. Body mass index was defined as the body mass in Kg divided by the square of the body height in meter which is expressed in units of kg/m². BMI was as an indicator of overall health status at the population level. The higher the BMI, higher the risk of certain diseases. Calculated BMI of subjects with respect to WHO-BMI classification chart for Asians (World Health Organisation) was summarised as follows.

4.2 Anthropometric Data and BMI

This section contained 2 questions on height and weight

4.3 Distribution of subjects with respect to WHO-BMI classification (Asians)

BMI Category	Std. values kg/m ²	Female	Male
Underweight	<=18.5	21(29.16%)	17(23.61%)
Normal Weight	18.5 to 22.9	22(30.56%)	23(31.94%)
Overweight	23 to 24.9	9(12.5%)	4(5.56%)
Obesity class I	25-29.9	16(22.22%)	22(30.56%)
Obesity class II	Above 30	4(5.56%)	6(8.33%)
Total		72	72

In this study, out of 144 subjects, 29.16% female and 23.16% male had a BMI below. 18.5 and were categorized as Underweight. 30.56% and 31.94% in female and male respectively had a BMI between 18.5 and 24.9 and were categorized as Normal.12.5% of female and 5.56% had a BMI between 23 and 24.9 and

were categorized as Overweight. 22.22% females and 30.56% of males had a BMI between 25 and 29.9 and were categorized as Obesity Grade 1. 5.56% of females and 8.33% of males had a BMI above 30 and were categorized as Obesity Grade 2.

Table 4.4: Data on Average BMI with respect to Gender.

Gender	Average BMI	Std Dev	t-value (two tail)	p-value (two tail)
Male	22.81kg/m ²	4.8	1.9	0.2
Female	21.78 kg/m ²	4.9		

Average BMI Graph

Fig 4-Average BMI

The above figure shows average BMI of males and females. The average BMI of male was 22.81 kg/m² and average BMI of female was 21.78kg/m² and standard deviation of male was 4.8 and females was 4.9. To find a significant difference between the BMI of males and females, a parametric test, the t-test, was applied. Since the calculated value 0.2 was less than critical value of 1.6 at the significance level of 0.1, Null hypothesis was accepted, and we can conclude that there is no significant difference between BMI of male and female.

4.3 RESEARCH BASED QUESTIONS
RESEARCH BASED QUESTION WERE DIVIDED INTO 4 SETS

- I. Questions to list most Common Social Media (SM).
- II. Questions on Awareness about nutrition and health and reason behind reading NM (nutritional messages).
- III. Questions on Acceptance of NM on SM
- IV. Questions on Application of nutritional messages on SM

SET I- To list most common SM

1. Do you follow social media?

Fig 5 Percentage distribution of total subjects who follow social media.

It is observed that the most percentage of respondents (93.06%) had been following SM and the least

percentage of only 6.94% were not following any social media.

Fig 6. Percentage distribution as per gender of people who follow social media.

Among the responses, 47% of male followed social media, while 3 % did not follow. In female population,

47% followed social media and 3 % did not follow social media.

2. Which social media you follow the most? (Can choose more than one options)

Fig 7. Percentage distribution of most common SM from total list.

The data highlighted the popularity of different social media platforms among users and their patterns of use: WhatsApp: Followed by 97% of people YouTube: Followed by 79% of people Both WhatsApp and YouTube: 14.93% WhatsApp, Facebook, YouTube, and Instagram: 12.69% WhatsApp, Instagram, and YouTube: 11.19%.

(93.06%) follow social media and both male and female respondents exhibit equal levels of social media engagement with 47% of each gender following SM. The most common social media are WhatsApp, which is 97%, followed by YouTube i.e. 79%, and then Facebook i.e. – 37.9% and most of the people followed more than one or two social medias.

Discussion on objective 1- To list the most used social media: It was observed that vast majority of respondents

SET II- Awareness about nutrition and health and reason behind reading nutritional messages

1. Do you know how many calories you need in 24 hrs?

Fig 8. Percentage distribution of calories in subjects.

As per above graph, 34.7% of subjects were aware of how many calories they need in 24 hrs, while 65.3 % did

not know how many calories they need in 24 hours.

Fig 9- Percentage distribution of subject about awareness of calories as per gender.

It is observed that specifically, 19.44% of males were aware of the recommended daily caloric intake, while 30.56% lacked this knowledge. Among females, 15.28%

were informed about their daily caloric needs, but a higher percentage, 34.72%, were unaware.

2. Do you believe that regular exercise keeps you healthy?

Fig 10- Percentage distribution of subject who have awareness about exercise.

It was found that majority, 85.42% of the subjects believes regular excerside could keep them healthy while

14.58% said they did not believe that rugular excesie coul keep them healthy.

Fig 11- Percentage distribution of subject about exercise awareness as per gender.

According to the data, a majority portion of both males and females in the urban population recognised the health benefit of regualr exercise. Among males, 42.36%

believed that regualr exerise could keep them healthy, whereas a small percentage, 7.64%, did not share this belief. Similarly, 43.06% of females acknowledged the

positive impact of regular exercise on their health, with only 6.94% disagreeing. These figures suggested a high level of awareness and agreement across both genders

about the importance of regular exercise for maintaining health, though a small minority in each group remains unconvinced.

3. Does oily food end up with obesity?

Fig 12- Percentage distribution of subject who think oily food causes obesity.

The data indicated strong consensus among the urban population regarding the impact of oily food on obesity. A substantial 82.64% of respondents believed that consuming oily food could lead to obesity, reflecting a

widespread awareness of the potential negative health effects associated with such dietary choices. Conversely, 17.36% of the respondents did not believe that oily food consumption contributed to obesity.

Fig 13 - Percentage distribution of subject as per gender who thinks oily food causes obesity.

As per above figure in male, 39.58% believed oily foods ends up in obesity while 10.42% did not believe. In

female 43.06% believed oily food ends up in obesity while 6.94% did not believe.

4. Why do you read nutritional post on social media?

Fig 14- Percentage distribution of subject for reason of reading nutritional post on SM.

In this study the data revealed, 45.83% said they read nutrition related post on SM for gaining good health

while, 49.31% people said they read for knowledge, and 4.86% said other reasons.

Fig 15- Percentage distribution of subject for reasons to read nutritional post on SM.

According to data of males and females for reasons behind reading messages on SM it was revealed that, in male 25% said they read nutrition related posts for knowledge, while 22.22% said for good health and 2.78% said other reasons while in females 24.31% said

they read nutrition related post for knowledge, 23.61% said they read for good health and 2.08% said other reasons.

5. How frequently do you see post related to food, diet or nutrition?

Fig 16- Percentage distribution of total subject who see post on food on SM.

The study revealed very few numbers of subject did not see message while most often see or sometime sees. As per above figure 29.86% of people often saw post related

to food, nutrition and diet, while 51.39% saw sometimes while 18.75% saw rarely food related post on SM.

Fig 17- Percentage distribution of subjects as per gender who sees post related to food on SM.

As per the above, 16.7% of males often viewed food-related posts on social media, while 22.2% sometimes viewed them, and 11.1% rarely viewed food-related posts. Among females, 13.2% often viewed food-related posts, 29.2% sometimes viewed them, while 7.6% rarely viewed food-related posts on social media.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION ON SET II: Awareness about health and nutrition

To know the awareness about health and nutrition of respondents in Nagpur city, we framed the above question and observed that majority of respondents 85.42%, were aware about regular exercise and its importance in daily routine in both genders. A significant portion (82.64%) of population believed oily food ends up with obesity with females showed a slightly higher belief than males. A significant portion (65.3%) of the

population was unaware of their daily caloric needs, with females being slightly less informed than males.

The majority (49.31% & 45.31% respectively) of respondents read nutrition-related posts for gaining knowledge and improving health. This trend highlighted the role of social media in disseminating health information.

Most respondents saw nutrition-related posts sometimes or often, indicating a moderate to high level of engagement with health content on social media. Females tend to be engaged more frequently with such content compared to males. The subjects were aware about nutrition and health and had interest in it but lacked detail knowledge.

Set III-Acceptance of nutrition-based messages on SM

1. Do you share or forward nutrition related messages as it is?

Fig 18- Percentage distribution of total subject who share messages as it is on SM.

Data revealed that notable 42.36% of respondents forward nutrition-related messages without modification.

And the majority, 57.64%, choose not to share messages as received.

Fig 19- Percentage distribution of subjects as per gender who forward messages as it is.

As per data from above graph, 21.53% of males shared messages as it was while 28.47% don't share messages

as it was. In females 20.83% share messages as it is while 29.17% don't. share messages as it was.

2. Do you verify messages before forwarding?

Fig 20- Percentage distribution of total subject who verify messages before forwarding.

As per above above diagram, 18.75% verified messages before forwarding while 50.0% did not verified messages while 31.25% verified messages sometime before forwarding.

came to verifying messages before sharing them with others. A small percentage, 18.75%, of subjects consistently verified messages before forwarding them. Half of the respondents, 50.0%, did not verify messages before forwarding them. A significant portion, 31.25%, sometimes verified messages before forwarding them.

The data revealed diverse range of behaviors when it

Fig 21- Percentage distribution of subjects as pe gender who verify messages before forwarding.

As per above graph, in males 10.42% verified messages before forwarding while 24.31% did not verified messages and 15.28% verified sometimes only before

forwarding. In females 8.33% shared verified messages while 25.69% did not verified messages and 15.97% verifiedonly sometime.

3. Do you follow any food related accounts or influencers on social media?

Fig 22- Percentage distribution of total subjects who follow food related account or influencer on SM.

The data indicated that a significant portion of the population, 42.36%, followed food-related accounts or social media influencers. On the other hand, 57.64% of

people did not follow food-related accounts or social media influencers.

Fig 23- Percentage distribution of subject as per gender who follows food related account or influencer on SM.

Above data revealed, 21.53% of males followed social media influencer while 28.47% did not follow social media influencer. In females, 22.83% followed social

media influencer while 29.17% did not follow social media influencer or food related account.

4. Who do you trust more for nutritional advice-Dietician, Doctor, Family

Fig 24- Percentage distribution of total subject to whom they trust for nutritional advises on SM.

The data obtained from graph indicated majority 52.1% of people placed their trust in dieticians for nutritional advice, while significant 27.8% of people trusted doctors

for nutritional advice and small group 20.1% of people trusted their families.

Fig 25- Percentage distribution of subject as per gender to whom they trust for nutritional advises on SM.

According to gender-based data obtained from graph, it showed that among male dietitians are the most trusted source for nutritional advice at 26.4% which is followed by doctors at 14.6%, and family members at 9%. For females, dietitians are also the most trusted at

25.7% for nutritional advice while Doctors are trusted by 13.25% and family members by 11.1%.

5. Have you ever felt pressure to conform to certain dietary trends or body image standards promoted on social media?

Fig 26- Percentage distribution of total subject who feels pressurised for body images or to follow dietary trends on SM.

As per above figure Only 26.4% of respondents acknowledged becoming more conscious of these trends,

while a significant 73.6% remained unaffected.

Fig 27- Percentage distribution of subject as per gender who feels pressurised for body images or to follow dietary trends on SM.

The above figure illustrates the percentage of males and females who have become conscious of body image standards and dietary trends due to social media. Among

males, 12.5% said yes, while 37.5% said no. For females, 13.9% acknowledged this influence, whereas 36.1% did not.

6. Do you trust dietary advice or information shared on social media?

Fig 28- Percentage distribution of total subject who trust information shared on SM.

The data highlighted, 15.3% often trusted advises or information on SM, while 60.42% sometimes trusted

advises or information on SM and 24.31% said they never trusted any advice or information on SM.

Fig 29- Percentage distribution of subject as per gender who trust information shared on SM.

The above data revealed, 9.72% of males said they often trusted the nutritional advises they received on SM, while 31.25% said they sometimes trusted and 9.74% said they never trusted. In females 5.56% said often trusted, while 29.17% said sometimes trusted and 15.28% said they never trusted dietary advice on social media.

Discussion on set III-Acceptance of nutrition-based messages on SM

Forwarding Behaviour: A significant portion (57.64%) of respondents choose not to forward nutrition-related messages as received, indicated a cautious approach to sharing information. Both males and females exhibited similar behaviours in this regard.

Verification of Messages: The majority (50%) of respondents did not verified messages before forwarding, which could contribute to the spread of misinformation. There was a need for increased awareness about the importance of verifying information, especially in the context of health and nutrition.

Following Influencers: Less than half of the respondents (42.36%) followed food-related accounts or influencers, suggesting that these accounts had a limited

reach within the population. Both genders showed similar patterns in following influencers.

Trust in Nutritional Advice: Dietitians were the most (52.1%) trusted source of nutritional advice, followed by doctors and family members. This trend indicated a preference for professional advice over informal sources like social media influencers.

Impact of social media: Social media had a moderate (26.4%) influence on respondents' awareness of dietary trends, with a notable portion of both males and females acknowledged its impact. However, a majority (73.6%) remained unaffected, highlighted a varied response to social media content.

Trust in Social Media Advice: Most respondents are cautious about trusting nutritional advice on social media, with most of the number (60.42%) only sometimes trusting the information. This cautious approach reflected an awareness of the potential for misinformation on these platforms.

Set IV. Application of dietary habits from SM

1. Have you ever tried diet or recipe shared on social media?

Fig 30- Percentage distribution of total subject who tried diet plan as per SM.

The data indicated overall 49.3% tried recipe or diet plan on social media whereas 50.7% didn't tried any diet or recipe on social media.

Fig 31- Percentage distribution of subject as per gender who tried diet plan on SM.

The above figure shows, in males, 22.9 % tried diet plan or recipes from SM while 27.1 % did not tried SM while 23.6% didn't tried any diet plan or recipes. while in females 26.4 % tried diet plan or recipes from SM while 23.6% didn't tried any diet plan or recipes.

2. Have you ever purchased food or beverage products based on recommendation or advertisement you saw on social media?

Fig 32- Percentage distribution of total subject who purchased foods as per advertisement on SM.

The data indicated that majority, 66.7%, did not purchase food or beverage products based on social media advertisements, while 33.3% purchased food products on seeing advertisement on social media.

Fig 33- Percentage distribution of subjects as per gender who purchased foods on seeing advertisement on SM.

The data indicated in males overall, 22% purchased food products on seeing advertisement on social media, While 28% did not purchased food products on seeing advertisement on social media. In females, 21%

purchased food products on seeing advertisement on social media, while 29% did not purchase food products on seeing advertisement on social media.

3. Do you think your dietary habits have changed since you started using social media?

Fig 34- Percentage distribution of total subject who think their dietary habits have changed after SM.

The above graph obtained from this study showed that, 34.72% Said yes, as they were benefited positively by change in their dietary habits through social media, 11.81

% said yes for change in their diet habits but negatively and while 53.47% said there was no change in their dietary habits because of social media.

Fig 35- Percentage distribution of subject as per gender who think their dietary habits have changed after SM.

The data revealed that in males, 16.67% Said yes, they were benefited positively in their dietary habit from social media, 2.78 % said yes for change in their dietary habits negatively due to social media and 30.56% said there was no change in their dietary habits due to social media.

In females, 18.06% Said yes, they were benefited positively in their dietary habits from social media, 9.03% said yes for change in their dietary habits negatively due to social media and while 22.92% said there was no change in dietary habits due to social media.

4. Do you feel social media is taking you away from traditional nutritious food?

Fig 36- Percentage distribution of total subject who think SM has taken them away from traditional food.

The data indicated that significant population 46.5% of subjects thinks yes, SM was taking them away from

traditional food while slight majority 53.5% thinks SM was not taking them away from traditional food.

Fig 37- Percentage distribution of subject as per gender who think SM has taken them away from traditional food.

The Gender data revealed that, in males, 25.7% thinks yes for social media took them away from traditional food while 24.3% said they did not feel SM is took them away from traditional food. In females, 20.8%

thought SM took them away from traditional food while 29.2 said no for SM took them away from traditional food.

5. How often do you find craving certain food or snacks after seeing them on social media?

Fig 39- Percentage distribution of total subjects who craves certain food or snacks seen on SM.

The data obtained on frequency of craving indicated that, 22.92% of population often experienced craving certain food and snack after seeing them on social media, while majority 59.72% said they experienced craving certain

food and snacks, sometime, and 17.36% said they never experienced certain food and snacks craving after seeing them on SM.

Fig 40- Percentage distribution of subjects per gender who craves certain food or snacks seen on SM.

The gender insights into data revealed that in males, 9.03% often experience craving after they saw them on SM, 30.56% said they experience craving sometime while 9.03% said they never experience craving after

they saw on SM. In females, 12.50% often experience cravings, 29.17% said they sometimes experience cravings, while 8.33% never experience cravings for food and snacks after watching them on SM.

6. When you encounter food-related post on social media, how do they typically make you feel?

Fig 41- Percentage distribution of total subject’s feeling on encountering food related post on SM.

The data indicated majority (45.14%) of population feels inspired to try new recipes. A significant portion (33.33%) felt hungry, highlighting the immediate impact of visual food stimuli. A smaller group (15.97%) felt

indifferent, showed no emotional response, while an even smaller group (5.56%) felt guilty about their eating habits.

Fig 42 - Percentage distribution of subject’s feeling as per gender on encountering food related post on SM.

In males, 3.47% said they felt guilty about their eating habits when they saw food-related posts on social media, while in females, 2.08% reported the same feeling. Additionally, 16.67% of males and 16.67% of females said they felt hungry when they saw food-related posts on social media. When it came to feeling indifferent about these posts, 11.81% of males and 4.17% of females reported this sentiment. Lastly, 18.06% of males said they felt inspired to try new recipes when they see food-related posts on social media, compared to 27.08% of females.

Nearly half (49.3%) of the respondents had tried recipes or diet plans from social media, indicated significant engagement with content related to diet and nutrition. The slight difference between males and females suggested a balanced interest across genders.

Discussion on set IV-Application of nutritional messages on SM

Engagement with Social Media Recipes and Diet Plans:

Influence of Social Media Advertisements on Purchases: A majority (66.7%) did not purchase food products based on social media ads, indicated scepticism or a preference for trusted sources when making purchasing decisions. Both genders showed similar purchasing behaviour, with a slight difference in percentages.

Impact on Dietary Habits: Social media had a mixed impact on dietary habits, with more (34.72%)

respondents reported positive changes than negative ones. However, a majority reported no change, suggesting that while social media could influence some individuals, many remain unaffected.

Perception of Traditional Food: The population is divided on whether social media was impacting their consumption of traditional foods. This indicated a balance between maintaining traditional eating habits and exploring new ones influenced by social media.

Food Cravings: Most (22.92%) respondents experienced cravings after seeing food posts on social media, either often or sometimes, which highlighted the power of visual stimuli in influencing food choices. Both genders experienced cravings, with females slightly more likely

to experience them often.

Emotional Responses: A significant portion (45.14%) felt inspired to try new recipes, which showed a positive influence of social media on culinary exploration. Feelings of hunger was also common, which indicated that food posts could trigger immediate cravings. A smaller group felt indifferent or guilty, with guilt was being the least common response.

Comparison of responses of male and female by Chi-Square test

Out of all questions, responses for 8 questions were taken for checking the significance test, as rest of questions were about individual choices with multiple answer.

4.5 Responses of male and females with chi-square test values

Question	Male		Female		Chi square test	P
	YES	NO	YES	NO		
1. Do u know how many calories you take you need in 24 hrs.	28	44	22	50	0.58	0.29
2. Have you ever tired diet plan or recipe u discovered on SM	33	39	38	34	0.52	0.40
3. Have you purchased product or beverage advertise on SM	24	48	24	48	0.31	1
4. Do you share or forward nutritional post on SM	31	41	30	42	0.35	0.86
5. Do you feel SM is taking you away from traditional food	37	35	30	42	0.62	0.24
6. Do you follow any food related account or influencer on SM	31	41	30	42	0.35	0.86
7. Do you believe regular exercise keeps you healthy	22	50	20	52	0.39	0.71
8. Do oily food end up in obesity	18	54	22	50	0.49	0.49

- For question 1 (Do u know how many calories you take you need in 24 hrs.) The male responses were - 28 (YES), 44 (NO) and female responses were-22 (YES), 50 (NO). After chi-test, the value of P value – 0.587914275 and chi square test - 0.29, As the p-value is greater than 0.05 so the result between male and female responses was insignificant.
- For question 2 (Have you ever tried diet plan or recipe you discovered on SM.). The male responses were - 28 (YES), 44 (NO) and female responses were-22 (YES), 50 (NO). After chi-test the value of P value - 0.587914275 and chi square test - 0.29 As the p-value was greater than 0.05 so the result between male and female responses was insignificant.
- For question 3 (Have you purchased product or beverage advertise on SM.). The male responses were-24 (YES), 48 (NO) and female responses were-24 (YES), 48 (NO). After chi-test the value of P value -1 and chi square test -0.31 As the p-value was greater than 0.05 so the result between male and female responses was insignificant.
- For question 4 (Do you share or forward nutritional post on SM.). The male responses were-31 (YES), 41 (NO) and female responses were-30 (YES), 42 (NO). After chi-test the value of P value - 0.86607471 and chi square test - 0.35 As the p-value was greater than 0.05 so the result between male and female responses was insignificant.
- For question 5 (Do you feel SM is taking you away from traditional food.) The male responses were-37 (YES), 35 (NO) and female responses were - 30 (YES), 42 (NO). After chi-test the value of P value - 0.24 and chi square test -0.62 As the p-value was greater than 0.05 so the result between male and female responses was insignificant.
- For question 6 (Do you follow any food related account or influencer on SM.). The male responses were-31 (YES), 41 (NO) and female responses were-30 (YES), 42 (NO). After chi-test the value of P value -0.8660747 and chi square test - 0.35 As the p-value is greater than 0.05 so the result between male and female responses was insignificant.
- For question 7 (Do you believe regular exercise keeps you healthy.). The male responses were-22 (YES), 50 (NO) and female responses were-20 (YES), 52 (NO). After chi-test the value of P value – 0.7138582 and chi square test - 0.398165959. As the p-value was greater than 0.05 so the result between male and female responses was insignificant.
- For question 8 (Do oily food end up in obesity.). The male responses were-28 (YES), 44 (NO) and female responses were-22 (YES), 50 (NO). After chi-test the value of P value - 0.4567504 and chi square test - 0.49. As the p-value is greater than 0.05 so the result between male and female responses was insignificant. In all the 8 questions, the p-value was greater than 0.05 so the results in responses of male

and female was insignificant.

5.1 SUMMARY

5. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

For this study, selected area was Nagpur city with the sample size of 144. A descriptive cross-sectional study was done with the survey method. A structured questionnaire of 22 questions was developed to serve the objectives framed and then it is circulated to subjects thought social media and thus data was collected. Primary data was studied from results, and conclusions were found. The hypothesis of the study was tested using a parametric t-test and chi-square test. The results are summarized as follow.

5.1.1 Demographic Data

The study's demographic data includes a diverse sample of individuals aged 15 to 45, with unequal representation of males and females, and varying educational qualifications.

Age - 56.94% of participants (82 individuals) are aged 15-25, 20.13% (29 individuals) are aged 26-35, and 22.93% (33 individuals) are aged 36-45.

Gender - There is Equal representation with 72 males and 72 females.

Qualification - 30.56% (44 individuals) are graduates, 22.22% (32 individuals) are postgraduates, 30.50% (44 individuals) are in the 10th class and 16.6% (24 individuals) are in the 12th class.

5.1.2 Health status and BMI

The study provides an insightful overview of the health status and Anthropometric data. A notable prevalence of chronic diseases, with a higher proportion in females is present. There is diverse BMI distribution, with significant portions of the population classified as underweight (33.33%) or overweight (42.33%), and obese. There is No significant difference in average BMI between males and females. The average BMI of male is 22.81 kg/m² and average BMI of female is 21.78 kg/m².

The distribution of BMI categories among the population indicates a variety of weight statuses, However, the acceptance of the null hypothesis suggests that there is no significant difference in BMI between males and females in this population. This finding implies that gender does not play a significant role in the BMI variations observed in this subject. Therefore, any interventions aimed at addressing BMI-related health issues can be designed without a need for gender-specific adjustments, at least based on the current data.

5.1.3 Most common SM

Significant majority (93.06%) of population are active social media users. Both male and female show equal engagement in SM usage and WhatsApp is most popular followed by YouTube. A considerable portion of respondents use multiple social media platforms, indicating diverse digital engagement habits.

5.1.4 Awareness about Nutritional knowledge and reasons behind reading nutritional posts on SM

The study reveals varying levels of awareness and beliefs about health and nutrition among the population. Key findings include: Majority of subjects are unaware of their daily caloric needs. A high percentage believe in the health benefits of regular exercise. Most respondents think oily foods lead to obesity. Social media is a common source for nutrition information, with many reading posts for knowledge and health improvement.

Engagement with nutrition-related posts on social media is generally high, with females showing slightly higher engagement.

The responses indicate a significant interest in health and nutrition among the respondents, with nearly half seeking knowledge and good health through social media posts. This suggests that social media is a valuable resource for health-related information for many individuals.

5.1.5 Acceptance of nutritional-based messages on social media

The study highlights diverse behaviours and attitudes towards acceptance of nutrition-based messages on SM. A majority does not forward messages as received and often do not verify messages before forwarding highlighting the need for improved digital literacy and critical evaluation of online content. Less than half follow food-related accounts or influencers. Dietitians are the most trusted source of nutritional advice, followed by doctors and family members. Social media has a moderate influence on dietary awareness, with many respondents becoming more conscious of trends. There is a general caution in trusting social media advice, with most respondents only sometimes trusting the information.

5.1.6 Application of social media messages in dietary habits

The responses indicate a substantial influence of social media on the dietary habits of respondents. Nearly half (49.3%) have tried recipes or diet plans they discovered on social media, suggesting that social media is a significant source of dietary experimentation and inspiration. This could be attributed to the accessibility and appeal of visually engaging content, as well as the influence of social media trends. While social media influences dietary habits positively for some, many remain unaffected. There is a notable scepticism towards purchasing food products based on social media ads. Traditional food consumption appears to be balanced with the influence of new trends from social media. Visual stimuli from food posts trigger cravings and inspire culinary exploration for many respondents. Emotional responses to food posts vary, with inspiration and hunger being the most common.

Purchasing behaviour is also affected, with 33.3% of

respondents buying food and beverage products based on social media recommendations or advertisements. This highlights the power of social media marketing in shaping consumer choices and driving sales.

The pressure to conform to certain dietary trends or body image standards is felt by 26.4% of respondents, which is concerning. This pressure can lead to unhealthy behaviours and a negative relationship with food and body image, emphasizing the need for promoting positive and realistic health messages on social media.

5.1.7. Compare responses of males and females by Chi-square test

The Chi-square test results for all 8 questions show that the p-values are greater than 0.05, indicating that there are no statistically significant associations in the responses between males and females for these questions. This suggests that the perceptions and behaviours regarding nutrition and social media messages are similar across genders in these subjects.

The questions cover a range of topics, from awareness of caloric needs to the influence of social media on dietary habits and the trustworthiness of nutritional advice sources. The consistent insignificance in gender differences suggests that both males and females share similar levels of awareness, engagement, and attitudes towards these topics.

5.2 CONCLUSION

1. The demographic analysis highlights Youthful Dominance with largest age group between 15-25 years. Gender balance ensures that the study is inclusive and considers gender-specific experiences and viewpoints, enhancing the overall validity of the findings. The educational diversity, provides a comprehensive view of the population which enriches the study by incorporating a wide range of experiences and insights, making the findings more generalizable.
2. The higher prevalence of chronic diseases in females underline the need for targeted health initiatives. The study assessed the BMI of the total population and found that most of the subjects were in the normal weight category, with significant proportions being underweight or overweight. The comparison of BMI between males and females showed no significant difference which suggests that health interventions and policies should consider both genders equally when addressing weight-related health issues. Overall, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of the population's health status, which can inform future research and public health strategies.
3. The high adoption rate of social media platforms among the respondents reflects the integral role of digital communication in their lives. The equal

engagement across genders underscores the widespread appeal and accessibility of social media. The predominance of WhatsApp and YouTube highlights the importance of messaging and video content in users' digital experiences. Additionally, the trend of multi-platform usage suggests that respondents seek varied functionalities from different social media platforms, tailoring their usage to meet specific social and informational needs. These insights can inform strategies for social media marketing, digital communication, and content creation, ensuring they cater to the preferences and behaviours of the target audience.

4. The data indicates a general awareness and proactive attitude towards health among the population, particularly regarding the benefits of exercise and the impact of diet on obesity. However, there is a notable gap in knowledge about daily caloric needs, which suggests the need for better education and resources to help individuals understand and manage their dietary requirements. Social media plays a significant role in providing health information, and its influence is evident in the high engagement with nutrition-related content. These insights can inform public health strategies to improve dietary awareness and promote healthier lifestyles through targeted education and leveraging social media platforms.
5. The data indicates a cautious approach towards sharing and trusting nutrition-related information on social media. There is a significant preference for professional advice from dietitians and doctors over social media influencers. The study also reveals a need for better education on verifying information before sharing it, to prevent the spread of misinformation. While social media does have an impact on dietary awareness, there is a considerable portion of the population that remains sceptical about the advice found on these platforms. These insights can inform strategies to improve the dissemination and verification of nutritional information, promoting a more informed and health-conscious public. There is a notable pressure to conform to dietary trends and body image standards, which needs to be addressed to prevent negative health impacts. However, many respondents also reported positive changes in their dietary habits due to social media.
6. Social media plays a significant role in influencing dietary habits, food purchases, and emotional responses to food-related content. While it positively impacts some individuals' dietary habits and inspires culinary exploration, many remain cautious about purchasing products based on social media ads and maintain their traditional eating habits. The visual appeal of food posts effectively triggers cravings and influences food choices, highlighting the power

of social media in shaping food-related behaviours. Users are influenced by advertisements for food products which can lead to increased consumption of junk food.

- No significant difference is found in responses of gender-based category hence it can be concluded that social media affects all the users naturally irrespective of gender and age. Given the lack of significant gender differences, future research could explore other demographic factors that might influence nutritional perceptions and behaviours, such as age, education level, and socioeconomic status. Understanding these factors can help tailor more effective public health strategies and social media campaigns to promote better nutritional habits and overall health.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

- Promote Verification of Information
 - ✓ Encourage users to verify nutrition-related information before sharing it to prevent the spread of misinformation.
 - ✓ Increase awareness about the importance of professional nutritional advice and the risks of relying solely on social media for dietary information.
- Leverage Influencers Responsibly
 - ✓ Collaborate with credible dietitians and nutritionists to share accurate and reliable dietary advice on social media platforms.
 - ✓ Promote the benefits of traditional foods while also encouraging the exploration of new, healthy dietary trends.
 - ✓ Develop collaborative content that involves both influencers and health professionals, making the content engaging yet reliable.
 - ✓ Organize social media challenges and campaigns that promote healthy eating habits and traditional foods, encouraging community participation and discussion.
- Address Emotional Responses
 - ✓ Develop content that promotes positive body image and realistic dietary trends, countering the often-unrealistic standards portrayed on social media mitigating feelings of guilt.
 - ✓ Create content that addresses the emotional impact of food posts, promoting a healthy relationship with food.
 - ✓ Mindful Eating Campaigns: Promote the concept of mindful eating and provide tips on how to manage cravings healthily.
- Monitor Advertising Practices
 - ✓ Ensure that social media advertisements for food products are transparent and backed by reliable nutritional information.
 - ✓ Implement regulations to limit the exposure of young people to advertisements for unhealthy foods and beverages on social media platforms by policy makers should be done.

- Regular Surveys: Conduct regular surveys to monitor the effectiveness of these strategies and understand changing user behaviours and perceptions.
- Feedback Mechanism: Establish a feedback mechanism where users can share their experiences and suggestions for improvement.
- Fund and support programs that promote digital literacy and nutrition education in schools and communities.
- Social media platform should promote Credible Content by developing algorithms that prioritize credible, science-based content related to nutrition and health. Collaborate with health professionals to identify and highlight reliable sources.

By implementing these recommendations, social media platforms can foster a more informed and health-conscious user base, promoting positive dietary habits and reducing the spread of misinformation.

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Appendix A

Questionnaire framed with Objectives

Section	Questions	Question for analysis with objectives		
		To list the most commonly used social media	To study the awareness about nutrition and health amongst the sample	To study the acceptance of nutrition-based message on social media and its application in dietary habits
GD	1.Age 2.Gender			
	3.Occupation			
	4.Any history of chronic illness			
Anthropometric measurement	5.Weight in Kg			
	6.Height in metres			
Research based questions	7.Do you follow social media?	Yes		
	8.which social media you follow most?	Yes		
	9. How frequently do you see post related to food and nutrition on social media?			Yes
	10. why do you read nutritional post on social media		Yes	
	11.Do you know how many calories you need in 24 hrs?		Yes	
	12.Do you believe that regular exercise keeps u healthy		Yes	
	13.Does oily food end up with obesity?		Yes	

	14. Have you ever purchased food or beverages product based on recommendation or advertisement you saw on social media			
	15. Have you ever tried recipe or diet plan; you discovered on social media?			Yes
	16. Have you ever felt pressure to conform to certain dietary trends or body image standards promoted on social media?			Yes
	17. Do you think your dietary habits have changed since you started using social media?			Yes
	18. Do you feel social media is taking you away from traditional nutritious food?		Yes	
	19. How often do you find craving certain food or snacks after seeing them on social media?			Yes
	20. When you encounter food-related post on social media, how do they typically make you feel			Yes
	21. Do you trust nutritional advice on social media			Yes
	22. Do you share or forward nutrition			Yes

	related messages as it is?			
	23. Do you verify messages before forwarding?			Yes
	24. Whom do you trust for dietary advice or information shared on SM?			Yes
	25. Do you follow any food related account or influencer on SM			Yes

B. Summary of responses of males and females on research-based questions.

Sr no.	Question	Option For Responses	Male	Female
1.	Do u follow social media	Yes & No	Yes-67-yes	Yes-67
2.	How frequently do you see post related to food and nutrition on social media?	Often, Rarely & Sometime	Often-24	Often-19
3.	Which social media u follow most	Can choose more than 1.	WhatsApp - 67	WhatsApp-66
4.	Do you follow any food related account or influencer on social media	Yes/No	Yes-31	Yes-30
5.	Do you know how many calories you need in 24 hrs?	Yes/No	Yes-28	Yes-22
6.	Do you believe that regular exercise keeps u healthy	Yes/No	Yes-61	Yes-62
7.	Does oily food end up with obesity?	Yes /No	Yes-57	Yes-62
8.	Do you believe that regular exercise keeps you healthy?	Yes/No	Yes-62	Yes-61
9.	Why do you read nutritional post on SM	Knowledge/ good health/ others	Knowledge and good health-68	Knowledge and good health-69
10.		Often/sometime	Often-22	Often-19

	How frequently do you see post related to nutrition or diet?	rarely		
11.	Have you ever purchased food or beverage products based on recommendation or advertisement you saw on social media?	Yes /No	Yes-24	Yes-24
12.	Have you ever tried recipe or diet plan; you discovered on social media?	Yes/ No	Yes-33	Yes-38
13.	Have you ever felt pressure to conform to certain dietary trends or body image standards promoted on social media?	Yes/No	Yes-18	Yes-20
14.	Do you think your dietary habits have changed since you started using social media?	Yes-positively /yes Negatively /No	Yes Positively - 24	Yes-26
15.	Do you feel social media is taking you away from traditional nutritious food?	Yes/No	Yes-37	Yes-30
16.	How often do you find craving certain food or snacks after seeing them on social media?	Often/Sometime /Never	Yes- 15	Yes-18
17.	When you encounter food-related post on social media, how do they typically make you feel	Inspire to try new recipes/Hungry/ Indifferent.	Inspire to try new recipes 26	Yes-39
18.	Do you share or forward nutrition related messages as it is?	Yes/No	Yes-31	Yes-30
19.	Do you verify messages before forwarding?	Yes/No/ sometime	Yes-15	Yes-12
20.	Do you trust dietary advice or information shared on social media?	Often - Yes/Sometime /Never	Yes- 14	Yes-8
21.	Whom do u trust more for nutritional advice-dietician, Doctor, Family	Dietician /Doctor/ Family	Yes -59	Yes-56